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COVER PAGE AND DECLARATION

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Introduction

According to Chappelow (2024), “Statistics is a branch of applied mathematics that involves the collection, description, analysis, and inference of conclusions from quantitative data. The mathematical theories behind statistics rely heavily on differential and integral calculus, linear algebra, and probability theory. People who do statistics are referred to as statisticians. They’re particularly concerned with determining how to draw reliable conclusions about large groups and general events from the behavior and other observable characteristics of small samples. These small samples represent a portion of the large group or a limited number of instances of a general phenomenon” (Chappelow, 2024). The process of statistical information has a history that goes back to the beginning of humanity. In ancient times, humanity compiled statistical data to provide descriptive information related to all kinds of things, such as taxes, wars, crops, agriculture, and even athletics. Nowadays, with the development of theorems, statistical methods can be used not only describe the main features of the data, but also allow us to move beyond the data collected into the concept of decision-making through generalization and prediction.

Statistical analysis is the action of gathering and examining a dataset to identify patterns and derive insightful conclusions. In today's world, statistical analysis is the collection of raw data and the search for interconnectedness between variables to present patterns and trends to the parties involved. Working across a wide range of fields, statistical analysts are responsible for exploring new scientific discoveries to help improve community health and as business decision-making guidelines. In statistical analysis, it has two types such as descriptive statistical analysis and inferential statistical analysis. Descriptive statistical analysis is used to summarize data set without making conclusions. On the other hand, inferential statistical analysis is used to make conclusions the results from descriptive statistical analysis (Staff, 2023). Descriptive Statistical analysis uses some formula such as Maximum, Minimum, Mean, Median, Mode, Standard Deviation, Range, Skewness, and so on whereas Inferential Statistical analysis uses Hypothesis Testing, Confidence Interval, Regression and Correlation, and so on (Hillier, 20).

Objective of this report is working on a real-world dataset for analyzing, summary finding by using statistical analysis techniques. The main points of analysis criteria include data cleaning and preparation, exploratory data analysis, hypothesis testing, regression analysis, and machine

learning. For the real-world dataset, this report uses an actual business dataset of a Company namely, **PTC WORKSHOPS** locates at Kampot province, Cambodia. Main features of this current management system of this company provide data management such as vehicle repair services and vehicle spare part sales and basic statistical analysis only include total of business income and expense and total of salary each month. The dataset that will be used for analyzing is the database of management system of the company that was developed by using PHP language and MySQL database. The dataset stores two main parts, first part are inventory and sale management, second are staff, attendance and payroll management. But this database is exported to CSV file to work with Python programming language for analysis's purpose. After completed this analyzing, the dataset will interpret to information such as Max, Min, Mean, Median, Mode, Standard Deviation, Hypothesis Testing, Confidence Interval, Regression and Correlation.

Main Body

Data Cleaning and Preparation

There are 15 tables in **PTCDB** dataset and some tables are already cleaned because of the data validation of the front-end web application. But some tables are still had missing value because that are optional data. In statistical analysis concept, data must be cleaned and well preparation such as handling of missing data, data normalization, and data transformation before use it to analyze and interpret the result of finding. All the tables in the database will not be used all, for some related tables that need to use in analysis will be exported manually to the Python project's folder for analysis later.

<input type="checkbox"/>	table_admin	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_attendance	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_car	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_invoice	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_invoice_detail	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_invoice_detail_temp	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_payment	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_product	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_salary	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_service_income	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_staff	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_staff_type	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_stock	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_summary	★	Browse
<input type="checkbox"/>	table_utility	★	Browse
	15 table(s)		Sum

Figure 1. List of all tables in **PTCDB** dataset

Handling of Missing Data

The analysis is not for all tables, some tables are used also to analyze follow to the matched criteria. In **table_staff** table has missing value or data in **staff_photo** column. So this case, this column should be store other value to identify as it is **missing** or **null** beside leave it blank. The solution for this case is updating blank value directly of **staff_photo** column to store **missing** word with the following SQL script in PHP MyAdmin interface:

```
update table_staff set staff_photo ='missing';
```

```
select * from table_staff;
```

	staff_id	staff_card_number	staff_full_name	date_of_birth	start_working_date	sex	place_of_birth	address	phone_number	staff_photo
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit Copy Delete	12	C 003	KIN SOVANNA	1991-09-01	2019-11-09	Male	Kampot	Kampot	097 31 68 111	missing
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit Copy Delete	15	C 004	SAKHON SEREYBOT	1993-10-19	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	097 46 31 333	missing
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit Copy Delete	18	C 006	MEAN CHAN TORN	1999-01-19	2020-02-01	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 53 73 320	missing
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit Copy Delete	19	C 007	BUN YIVLY	1992-12-05	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 90 15 505	missing
<input type="checkbox"/> Edit Copy Delete	21	C 008	SUM SOVANNARATH	1997-10-12	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	098 62 82 64	missing

Figure 2. Updating **missing** word to **staff_photo** column in **table_staff** table

Data Transformation and Normalization

In **table_staff** table, there are two new columns has been added, namely, **age** and **experiences** to store current age and current experiences of all staffs by using the following SQL script (Kumar, 2022):

```
alter table table_staff add column age int, add column experiences float;
```

```
update table_staff set age = date_format(from_days(datediff(now(), date_of_birth)), '%Y') + 0;
```

```
update table_staff set experiences = date_format(from_days(datediff(now(), start_working_date)), '%y') + 0;
```

date_of_birth	start_working_date	sex	place_of_birth	address	phone_number	staff_photo	salary	type_id	staff_order	age	experiences
1991-09-01	2019-11-09	Male	Kampot	Kampot	097 31 68 111	missing	220	1	3	32	4
1993-10-19	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	097 46 31 333	missing	220	1	4	30	5
1999-01-19	2020-02-01	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 53 73 320	missing	200	1	6	25	4
1992-12-05	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 90 15 505	missing	250	1	7	31	5
1997-10-12	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	098 62 82 64	missing	170	2	8	26	5
1999-12-28	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 36 22 164	missing	160	2	9	24	5
1999-09-03	2019-05-31	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 28 63 215	missing	170	2	10	24	5
1999-07-11	2020-06-08	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 89 24 148	missing	150	2	11	24	4
1993-12-08	2019-10-03	Male	Kampot	Kampot	016 62 65 20	missing	110	2	12	30	4
2004-12-24	2021-02-04	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 50 88 953	missing	70	3	14	19	3
2003-11-10	2019-12-01	Male	Kampot	Kampot	096 68 48 278	missing	110	3	15	20	4
1998-03-02	2021-07-11	Male	Kampot	Kampot	088â€ 74 80 469	missing	30	3	17	26	2
2001-05-25	2021-12-05	Male	Kampot	Kampot	088 30 43 226	missing	50	3	18	23	2

Figure 3. Adding **age** and **experiences** columns to **table_staff** table

Data normalization is a technique used to transform the values of a dataset into a common scale. This is important because the dataset in statistics is sensitive to the scale of the input features and

can produce better results when the data is normalized. In this case, percentile is one of the normalization techniques that is used to separate the data into 100 equal parts. For this file below is **salaryAndExp.csv** that is exported from **PTCDB** dataset. It has two column salary and experiences. There are 25 rows in this file before percentile processing. The percentile data normalization is used to remove some outliers by using from the 5% lowest percentile until the highest 95%.

salary	experiences
32	4
30	5
25	4
31	5
26	5
24	5
24	5
24	4
30	4
19	3
20	4
26	2
23	2
27	2
23	2
18	2
24	1
15	1
29	5
44	24
31	11
22	2
21	0

19	1
22	0

Table 1. Data in **salaryAndExp.csv**

The formula of percentile is $P = (n/N) \times 100$. Where **P** is percentile, **n** is number of values below number of fall values, **N** is total count of population. By using Python programming to solve this case is one of the best ways in analysis (GeeksforGeeks, 2024). A file names **normalize.py** is used to read **salaryAndExp.csv** as the table above and calculate the lowest percentile 5% and the highest 5% of the dataset. After finding the lowest 5% and the highest 5%, they will be removed from the dataset but keep the new data after this process is from 5% to 95% only. And the new data will be written back to the existing CSV after completing this task.

File name: normalize.py

```
import csv

import numpy

fields = ['salary', 'experiences']

with open('salaryAndExp.csv') as f:

    reader = csv.reader(f)

    i = next(reader)

    data = numpy.array(sorted(csv.reader(f),key=lambda x:float(x[0])))

q1 = numpy.percentile(data[:, 0].astype(float), 5)

q3 = numpy.percentile(data[:, 0].astype(float), 95)

filtered_data = data[(data[:, 0].astype(float) > q1) & (data[:, 0].astype(float) < q3)]

with open('salaryAndExp.csv', 'w', newline='\n') as f:
```

```
csv.writer(f).writerow(i)
```

```
csv.writer(f).writerows(filtered_data)
```

Now the **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset has the new data after do the percentile tasks within 19 rows as the following table.

salary	experiences
30	2
50	2
50	1
50	2
50	0
50	1
50	0
70	3
110	4
110	4
150	4
160	5
170	5
170	5
200	4
220	4
220	5
220	5
250	5

Table 2. **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset after percentile processing.

Exploratory Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

Mean formula is used to calculate average of provided group of numbers. Its formula is:

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\text{Sum of observations}}{\text{Number of observations}}$$

To test the formula, the **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset will be used to calculate mean of salary of all staffs in the company. These are the salary of all staffs in USD such as 30, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 70, 110, 110, 150, 160, 170, 170, 200, 220, 220, 220, 220, 250. Where Sum of Salary is 2380 USD and the number of staffs is 19 people. The calculation of Mean = 2380/19. So the result of Mean is 125.2631 USD.

Median formula is used to calculate the middle number of sorted group of numbers ascending or descending. Its formula is:

$$\text{Median} = (n+1)/2$$

To test this formula, the **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset will be used to calculate the median of salary of all staffs in the company. These are the salary of all staffs in USD such as 30, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 70, 110, 110, 150, 160, 170, 170, 200, 220, 220, 220, 220, 250. Where **n** is total number of provided group of numbers and the group of numbers must be sorted in ascending or descending. In this case they are sorted in ascending and $n = 19$ because there are 19 salary of staffs column in **table_staff** table. So the calculation is Median = (19+1)/2 and the result is 10th number in a sort group of numbers. The value of 10th number location is 110 USD.

Mode is used to calculate which number value that appear high frequency. **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset will be used to calculate the mode of salary of all staffs in the company. These are the salary of all staffs in USD such as 30, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 70, 110, 110, 150, 160, 170, 170, 200, 220, 220, 220, 250. So the result of mode is 50 because 6 staffs have the salary 50 USD more than the number other staffs.

Range formula is used to calculate the value of differences from minimum to maximum. Its formula is:

$$R = \text{Highest Value}(H) - \text{Lowest Value}(L)$$

Where **R** is the range, **H** is the highest value and **L** is the lowest value. To test this formula, the **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset will be used to calculate the range of salary of all staffs in the company. These are the salary of all staffs in USD such as 30, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 70, 110, 110, 150, 160, 170, 170, 200, 220, 220, 220, 250. These provided group of numbers must be sorted in ascending or descending before calculating the range, in this case they are sorted in ascending. For **salary** column, the highest value row is 250 USD and the lowest value row is 30 USD. So the calculation of Range = 250 – 30. So the result is of range is 220.

Variance formula is used to calculate to find a measure of scattering of data points from the mean. There are two type of variances such as population variance and sample variable. This case is working with population variance and its formula is:

$$\sigma^2 = \sum (x_i - \bar{X})^2 / n$$

x_i	$x_i - \bar{X}$	$(x_i - \bar{X})^2$
30	-95.2632	9075.069
50	-75.2632	5664.543
50	-75.2632	5664.543
50	-75.2632	5664.543
50	-75.2632	5664.543
50	-75.2632	5664.543
50	-75.2632	5664.543
50	-75.2632	5664.543
70	-55.2632	3054.017
110	-15.2632	232.964
110	-15.2632	232.964
150	24.7368	611.9114
160	34.7368	1206.648

170	44.7368	2001.385
170	44.7368	2001.385
200	74.7368	5585.596
220	94.7368	8975.069
220	94.7368	8975.069
220	94.7368	8975.069
250	124.737	15559.28
2380	0	100473.7

Table 3. The addition of sum of squares is all the squared differences.

The calculation of population variance is $100473.7 / 19 = 5288.089$ USD

Standard Deviation formula is used to calculate spread of values in a dataset relative to its mean. There are two type of standard deviation such as population and sample standard deviation. This case is working with population standard deviation and its formula is:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sum (x_i - \mu)^2 / N}$$

In short way, variance can be used to calculate standard deviation by using square root of variance. So, the calculation of population standard deviation is:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{5288.089} = 72.71 \text{ USD}$$

Skewness is used to find outliers and trending in a provided dataset. Its formula is:

$$3(\text{mean} - \text{median}) / \text{standard deviation}$$

So, the calculation is $3(125.263 - 110) / 72.71 = 0.211$. The result is positive skewness because mean is larger than the median, whereas the mode has the highest visual representation. That is because the tail of the distribution pulls the mean to the right.

All formulas above such as mean, median, mode, range, variance, standard deviation, and skewness can be applied with statistical applications or programming to calculate the result without calculating follow their formula manually. In the case, there is a Python file, namely **discriptive.php** that produces code with **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset to calculate mentioned formulas of the descriptive statistics.

File name: discriptive.php

```
import statistics

import csv

import numpy

from scipy.stats import skew

with open('salaryAndExp.csv') as f:

    reader = csv.reader(f)

    i = next(reader)

    data = numpy.array(sorted(csv.reader(f),key=lambda x:float(x[0])))

mean = statistics.mean(data[:, 0].astype(float))

median = statistics.median(data[:, 0].astype(float))

mode = statistics.mode(data[:, 0].astype(float))

range = numpy.max(data[:, 0].astype(float)) - numpy.min(data[:, 0].astype(float))

variance = statistics.pvariance(data[:, 0].astype(float))

stDev = statistics.pstdev(data[:, 0].astype(float))

skewNess = skew(data[:, 0].astype(float), axis=0, bias=True)
```

```

print('Mean is : ', mean)

print('Median is : ', median)

print('Mode is : ', mode)

print('Range is : ', range)

print('Variance is : ', variance)

print('Standard Deviation is : ', stDev)

print('Skewness is : ', skewNess)

```

The line of codes above produces the descriptive statistics result as the following figure.

```

Mean is : 125.26315789473684
Median is : 110.0
Mode is : 50.0
Range is : 220.0
Variance is : 5288.08864265928
Standard Deviation is : 72.71924533890103
Skewness is : 0.21170611670311906

```

Figure 4. Calculation of some descriptive statistics by using Python codes

Frequency Distribution is a table that display frequency number of group of values. Frequency number count by single value or by range of group of values. The **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset will be used to construct the frequency distribution table of salary of all staffs in the company as below table. These are the salary of all staffs in USD such as 30, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 50, 70, 110, 110, 150, 160, 170, 170, 200, 220, 220, 220, 250. So the result of frequency distribution table is displayed below.

salaries	frequencies
30	1

50	6
70	1
110	2
150	1
160	1
170	2
200	1
220	3
250	1

Table 4. Frequency distribution table of **salaryAndExp.csv**

Frequency distribution can be applied with statistical applications or programming to calculate the result without calculating follow their formula manually. For example, there is a Python file, namely **fre.php** that produces code with **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset to create frequency distribution table.

File name: fre.py

```
import pandas as pd

import csv

import numpy

pd = pd.read_csv('salaryAndExp.csv')

salary = pd['salary']

exp = pd['experiences']

data = salary.value_counts().sort_index().to_dict()

result_keyvalpairs = data.items()

list_data = list(result_keyvalpairs)
```

```
freTable = numpy.array(list_data)
```

```
fields = ['salaries', 'frequencies']
```

```
with open('freTable.csv', 'w', newline='\n') as f:
```

```
    csv.writer(f).writerow(fields)
```

```
    csv.writer(f).writerows(numpy.array(freTable.astype(float)))
```

The line of codes above produces the frequency distribution table and write all new data to a file name **freTable.csv** as the following result.

```
salaries,frequencies
30.0,1.0
50.0,6.0
70.0,1.0
110.0,2.0
150.0,1.0
160.0,1.0
170.0,2.0
200.0,1.0
220.0,3.0
250.0,1.0
```

Figure 5. Frequency distribution table is generated by using Python codes

Visualization and Summarize the Data

Data visualization is a way that used to present data visually through charts and graphs. There many types of charts and graphs include indicator, Line, Bar, Column, Pie, Area, Pivot, Scatter, Bubble, Polar, and so on (Team, 2024). In the following charts and graphs will display include

Pie Chart, Bar Chart, Histogram, Line Chart, Scatter Plot, Box Plot that are generated by using Python and CSV datasets to produce the result.

Pie Chart: Python file below uses **freTable.csv** dataset to produces a pie chart that summarize data in visualization mode by displaying about the salary frequency of all staffs in percentages such as staffs receive 30 USD have 5.3%, 50 USD have 31.6%, 70 USD have 5.3%, 110 USD have 10.5%, 150 USD have 5.3%, 160 USD have 5.3%, 170 USD have 10.5%, 200 USD have 5.3%, and staffs receive 250 USD have 5.3%.

File name: salaryPieChart.py

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import numpy as np

import pandas as pd

data = np.array(pd.read_csv('freTable.csv'))

salary = data[:,0]

freq = data[:,1]

def func(pct, allvalues):

    absolute = int(pct / 100.*np.sum(allvalues))

    return '{:d}P\n{:.1f} %'.format(absolute,pct)

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(10, 7))

wedges, texts, autotexts = ax.pie(freq, autopct=lambda pct: func(pct, freq),

ax.legend(wedges, salary,

          bbox_to_anchor=(1, 0, 0.3, 1),

          title='Salaries (USD)',
```

```

loc='center right',

)

ax.set_title('Salary Frequency Pie Chart')

plt.show()

```


Figure 6. Create salary frequency pie chart by using Python codes

Bar Chart: Python file below uses **freTable.csv** dataset to produce a bar chart that summarizes data in visualization mode by displaying about the salary frequency of all staffs in frequency such as staffs receive 30 USD have 1 person, 50 USD have 6 people, 70 USD have 1 person, 110 USD have 2 people, 150 USD have 1 person, 160 USD have 1 person, 170 USD have 2 people, 200 USD have 2 people, and staffs receive 250 USD have 1 person.

File name: salaryBarChart.py

```
import numpy as np
```

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

```
import pandas as pd

data = np.array(pd.read_csv('freTable.csv'))

salary = data[:,0]

freq = data[:,1]

height = freq

bars = salary

y_pos = np.arange(len(bars))

plt.title('Salary Frequency Bar Chart')

plt.xlabel('Salaries')

plt.ylabel('Frequencies')

plt.bar(y_pos, height)

plt.xticks(y_pos, bars)

plt.show()
```


Figure 7. Create salary frequency bar chart by using Python codes

Histogram: Python file below uses **freTable.csv** dataset to produces a histogram that summarize data in visualization mode by display about the salary frequency of all staffs in frequency such as staffs receive 30 USD have 1 person, 50 USD have 6 people, 70 USD have 1 person, 110 USD have 2 people, 150 USD have 1 person, 160 USD have 1 person, 170 USD have 2 people, 200 USD have 2 people, and staffs receive 250 USD have 1 person.

File name: salaryHistogram.py

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import pandas as pd

import numpy as np

data = np.array(pd.read_csv('freTable.csv'))

salaries = data[:,0]
```

```

frequencies = data[:,1]

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))

bars = plt.bar(salaries, frequencies, width=20, color='skyblue', edgecolor='black')

for bar, frequency in zip(bars, frequencies):

    plt.text(bar.get_x() + bar.get_width() / 2, bar.get_height() + 0.1, str(int(frequency)),

             ha='center', va='bottom', fontsize=10)

plt.xlabel('Salaries')

plt.ylabel('Frequencies')

plt.title('Salary Frequency Histogram')

plt.grid(True)

plt.show()

```


Figure 8: Create salary frequency histogram by using Python codes

Line Chart: Python file below uses **freTable.csv** dataset to produce a line chart that summarizes data in visualization mode by displaying about the salary frequency of all staffs in frequency such as staffs receive 30 USD have 1 person, 50 USD have 6 people, 70 USD have 1 person, 110 USD have 2 people, 150 USD have 1 person, 160 USD have 1 person, 170 USD have 2 people, 200 USD have 2 people, and staffs receive 250 USD have 1 person.

File name: salaryLineChart.py

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import numpy as np

import pandas as pd

data = np.array(pd.read_csv('freTable.csv'))

x = data[:,0]

y = data[:,1]

plt.title('Salary Frequency Line Chart')

plt.xlabel('Salaries')

plt.ylabel('Frequencies')

plt.scatter(x, y)

plt.show()
```


Figure 9: Create salary frequency line chart by using Python codes

Scatter Plot: Python file below uses **freTable.csv** dataset to produces a scatter plot chart that summarize data in visualization mode by display about the salary frequency such as staffs receive 30 USD have 1 person, 50 USD have 6 people, 70 USD have 1 person, 110 USD have 2 people, 150 USD have 1 person, 160 USD have 1 person, 170 USD have 2 people, 200 USD have 2 people, and staffs receive 250 USD have 1 person.

salaryScatterPlot.py

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import numpy as np

import pandas as pd

data = np.array(pd.read_csv('freTable.csv'))

x = data[:,0]
```

```
y = data[:,1]

plt.title('Salary Frequency Scatter Plot Chart')

plt.xlabel('Salaries')

plt.ylabel('Frequencies')

plt.scatter(x, y)

plt.show()
```


Figure 10. Create salary frequency line chart by using Python codes

Box Plot: Python file below uses **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset to produces a box plot that summarize data in visualization mode by display about the salary frequency of all staffs such as minimum salary of all staffs is 30 USD, Q1 salary of all staffs is 110 USD, median salary of all staffs is 170 USD, Q3 salary of all staffs is 220 USD, and maximum salary of all staffs is 250 USD.

File name: salaryBoxPlot.py

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import numpy as np

import pandas as pd

data = np.array(pd.read_csv('freTable.csv'))

salaries = data[:,0]

frequencies = data[:,1]

data = []

for salary, frequency in zip(salaries, frequencies):

    data.extend([salary] * int(frequency))

q1 = np.percentile(data, 25)

median = np.percentile(data, 50)

q3 = np.percentile(data, 75)

data_min = np.min(data)

data_max = np.max(data)

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))

plt.boxplot(data, vert=False, patch_artist=True, showmeans=True)

plt.xlabel('Salary')

plt.title('Salary Box Plot')

plt.text(q1, 1, f'Q1={q1}', ha='center', va='bottom', color='blue', fontsize=10)
```

```

plt.text(median, 1, f'Median={median}', ha='center', va='bottom', color='blue', fontsize=10)

plt.text(q3, 1, f'Q3={q3}', ha='center', va='bottom', color='blue', fontsize=10)

plt.text(data_min, 1, f'Min={data_min}', ha='center', va='bottom', color='blue', fontsize=10)

plt.text(data_max, 1, f'Max={data_max}', ha='center', va='bottom', color='blue', fontsize=10)

plt.grid(True)

plt.show()

```


Figure 11. Create salary frequency box plot by using Python codes

Hypothesis Testing

Appropriateness of the Test

Hypothesis testing is the one of many techniques in statistics analysis that used to make conclusions of population data. It is used by researcher to verifies hypotheses and assesses the probable outcome of events that fall to the certain range of accuracy (Hypothesis Testing -

Definition, Examples, Formula, Types, n.d.). To implement the real case, dataset below is from a **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset that is used to test the hypothesis.

salary	experiences
30	2
50	2
50	1
50	2
50	0
50	1
50	0
70	3
110	4
110	4
150	4
160	5
170	5
170	5
200	4
220	4
220	5
220	5
250	5

Table 5. Data of **salaryAndExp.csv** dataset

This case study, the researcher claims that the mean average salary of staffs is greater than 130 USD with a standard deviation of 72.71 USD. There are 19 staffs are chosen with an average salary of 125.26 USD. Hypothesis testing is used to check if there is enough evidence to support the claim of the researcher. The provided confidence interval is 95%. The solution is detailed in steps below:

Step 1: Set the null hypothesis is $H_0: \mu_0 = 130$ but the alternative hypothesis is $H_1: \mu_0 \neq 130$.

Step 2: The population variance is known but the sample size is lower than 30, so the appropriate test statistic is t-test.

Step 3: $\alpha = 100\% - 95\% = 5\%$. This can be used to determine the critical value. $1 - \alpha = 1 - 0.05 = 0.95$.

Step 4: The standard normal distribution table is needed to use determine the critical values. This is a two-sided test, so the significance level (α) is divided equally between the two tails. The critical value from the standard normal distribution table for probability is:

$$(p) = 1 - 0.05 / 2$$

$$T_{0.025} = 2.1009$$

The critical values for a two-sided test are:

$$-t_{\alpha/2} = -2.1009 \text{ and } t_{\alpha/2} = 2.1009$$

The decision rule of the hypothesis test is:

$$\text{If } T \leq -t_{0.025} \text{ or } T \geq t_{0.025}, \text{ reject } H_0$$

$$\text{If } T > -t_{0.025} \text{ or } T < t_{0.025}, \text{ Fail to reject } H_0$$

The decision rule (based on p-value approach) is:

$$\text{p-value} \leq \alpha, \text{ Reject } H_0$$

$$\text{p-value} > \alpha, \text{ Fail to reject } H_0$$

Step 5: Calculate the t test statistic. The sample and population means are known along with the standard deviation.

$$T = \frac{\bar{x} - \mu_0}{s/\sqrt{n}} = \frac{125.26 - 130}{72.71/\sqrt{19}} = -0.2842$$

Interpretation of Results and Statistical Significance

Make a decision based on the result:

Critical value approach:

$$\text{If } -0.2842 \leq -2.1009 \text{ or } -0.2842 \geq 2.1009, \text{ then reject } H_0$$

Fail to reject H_0 because the calculated t-statistic falls between the two critical values.

P-value approach: p – value = 0.7763

P – value > 0.05, Failed to reject H_0

Conclusion: Fail to reject H_0 because the p-value is higher than the specified significance level (α).

Python programming language is also can be used to calculate the hypothesis test as in a file name **test.py** below.

File name: test.py

```
import numpy as np
```

```
from scipy.stats import t
```

```
null_mean = 130
```

```
population_std_dev = 72.7100
```

```
n = 19
```

```
sample_mean = 125.2600
```

```

t_statistic = (sample_mean - null_mean) / (population_std_dev / np.sqrt(n))

df = n - 1

alpha = 0.05

critical_value_lower = t.ppf(alpha / 2, df)

critical_value_upper = t.ppf(1 - alpha / 2, df)

print('T-Statistic:', round(t_statistic, 4))

print('Critical Values (Two-tailed):', round(critical_value_lower, 4), 'and',
round(critical_value_upper, 4))

if t_statistic < critical_value_lower or t_statistic > critical_value_upper:

    print('Reject the null hypothesis')

else:

    print('Fail to reject the null hypothesis')

```

After executing the line of codes above it displays the result the hypothesis test.


```

T-Statistic: -0.2842
Critical Values (Two-tailed): -2.1009 and 2.1009
Fail to reject the null hypothesis
PS C:\Users\W10\Desktop\ana>

```

Figure 12. Hypothesis testing result by using Python codes

Regression Analysis

Regression analysis is a technique for predictive modeling that measures the correlation between variables. This modeling is used like a tool to predict values in numeric type based on a variety

of inputs. The relationship between an independent and dependent variable can be used to predict how the dependent variable changes follow with its independent counterpart.

Selection of Appropriate Models and Feature Engineering

There are many types of regression models such as Simple Regression, Multiple Regression, Linear Regression, Multiple Linear Regression, logistic Regression and so no. Simple regression model is used to estimate the relationship between a dependent variable and one independent variable. Multiple regression model is used to determine the relationship between a dependent variable and more than one independent variable. Linear regression is a simple regression type that used to create a hypothetical line that best connects all data points. multiple linear regression shows the direct or linear correlation between variables is possible. Logistic regression is used to measure the relationship between dependent and independent variables though it does not correlate between independent variables. In this case, linear regression will be used regression for regression analysis.

Model Fitting

The simplest kind of regression is called linear regression, and it is used to draw a hypothetical line that most closely connects each data point. The formula of linear regression model is:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 * X_1 + \epsilon$$

Y is the variable that used to predict and is called the dependent variable. **X** is an independent variable. When using **regression analysis**, the purpose is to predict the value of **Y** by providing the value of **X** (Valchanov, 2021).

Evaluation of Model Performance

The experiences of staffs grow depends on the number of age of staffs. The dependent variable is experiences, while the independent variable is age of staffs. There is a relationship between these two variables. The more experience that staffs get based on their age while they are working. They want to get experiences, so they must work in their ages. The **ageAndExp.csv** dataset is used to work with this linear regression analysis. The dataset has the follow data.

age	experiences
15	1
18	2
19	1
19	3
20	4
22	2
23	2
23	2
24	1
24	4
24	5
24	5
25	4
26	2
26	5
27	2
29	5
30	4
30	5
31	5
32	4

Table 6. The **ageAndExp.csv** dataset

The python file below names **regression.py** uses **ageAndExp.csv** dataset to analyze by using linear analysis model.

File name: regression.py

```
import numpy as np
```

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plot
```

```
import pandas as pa

from scipy import stats

pd = pa.read_csv('ageAndExp.csv')

features = pd['age']

labels = pd['experiences']

fig = plot.figure('Regression')

slope, intercept, r, p, std_err = stats.linregress(features, labels)

def lineFunc(x):

    return slope * x + intercept

lineY = list(map(lineFunc, features))

print(lineY)

plot.scatter(features,labels)

plot.plot(features,lineY)

plot.title('Regression')

plot.xlabel('Age')

plot.ylabel('Experiences')

plot.show()
```

The result of Python code generates the linear regression in the following chart.

Figure 13. Python code generates the linear regression chart.

Machine Learning

As stated by GeeksforGeeks, “Machine learning is a type of artificial intelligence that enables algorithms that allows computer systems learn and improve their performance on a specific task. Machine learning has been found in applications in several fields include image and speech recognition, recommendation systems, fraud detection, automating tasks and so on”

(GeeksforGeeks, 2024a). In this case, **ageAndExp.csv** dataset will used by exporting to CSV file for machine learning including the selection of appropriate models, feature engineering, model fitting, and evaluation of model performance. This CSV file has only two columns such as **age** and **experiences** columns that will be used by machine learning for analysis.

Selection of Appropriate Models and Feature Engineering

Based Javapoint.com, “Machine Learning models can be understood as a program that has been trained to find patterns within new data and make predictions. These models are represented as a mathematical function that takes requests in the form of input data, makes predictions on input data, and then provides an output in response. First, these models are trained over a set of data,

and then they are provided an algorithm to reason over data, extract the pattern from feed data and learn from those data. Once these models get trained, they can be used to predict the unseen dataset. Based on different business goals and data sets, there are three learning models for algorithms. Each machine learning algorithm settles into one of the three models include Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning and Reinforcement Learning” (Machine Learning Models - Javatpoint, n.d.). In this case, Supervised Learning will be used regression for machine learning.

Model Fitting

Linear regression is a type of supervised machine learning algorithm that used with machine learning for training and testing. It is important to evaluate data and establish the relationship between two or more variables. Linear regression is chosen for model fitting to analyze in machine learning.

Evaluation of Model Performance

Some important libraries of Python are used in this file below, namely **ml.php** to implements machine learning by loading a dataset from **expAndAge.csv** dataset, splits the dataset into training and testing sets for model validation. Then Linear Regression model is trained both on the entire dataset (x and y) and separately on the training set (x_train and y_train). The last process, machine learning predicts values for new data points by using the trained model.

experiences	age
1	15
1	18
1	19
2	19
2	20
2	22
2	23
2	23

2	24
3	24
4	24
4	24
4	25
4	26
4	26
5	27
5	29
5	30
5	30
5	31
5	32

Table 7. Data in **expAndAge.csv** dataset

File name: ml.py

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

```
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
```

```
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, mean_absolute_error, r2_score
```

```
import math
```

```
df = pd.read_csv("expAndAge.csv")
```

```
df=np.array(df)
```

```
x = df[:,0]
```

```
y = df[:,1]

x_train, x_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(x, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=0)

print("X_train:",x_train.shape)

print("X_test:",x_test.shape)

print("Y_train:",y_train.shape)

print("Y_test:",y_test.shape)

model = LinearRegression()

model.fit(x_train.reshape(-1,1), y_train)

model.coef_

model.intercept_

y_pred = model.predict(x_test.reshape(-1,1))

mse = mean_squared_error(y_test, y_pred)

rmse = math.sqrt(mse)

mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test, y_pred)

r2 = r2_score(y_test, y_pred)

print("MSE --> ", mse)

print("RMSE --> ", rmse)

print("MAE --> ", mae)

print("R2 --> ", r2)

plt.scatter(y_test, y_pred)
```

```
plt.xlabel('Actual')
```

```
plt.ylabel('Predicted')
```

```
X_train: (16,)  
X_test: (5,)  
Y_train: (16,)  
Y_test: (5,)  
MSE --> 4.94712244897959  
RMSE --> 2.224212770617863  
MAE --> 1.7685714285714291  
R2 --> 0.7546070213799807  
Text(0, 0.5, 'Predicted')
```


Figure 14. Linear regression of machine learning generated by Python codes

```
sns.regplot(x=x, y=y, ci=None, color='blue')
```


Figure 15. Linear regression with line of machine learning generated by Python codes

Conclusion

Statistical analysis is one of the most important part in information technology or data science field. Its theory and formula can be applied in technological fields such as in research, machine learning, or data analysis especially it is used other fields include business, education, government or sport. Even though new technology grows rapidly, statistics is playing as an important role and still used along to it.

Descriptive statistical analysis, Inferential statistical analysis, Regression statistical analysis and machine learning are core concept that come from statistics plays as an important role to help many researchers success in their careers as Data Scientist.

References

- Chappelow, J. (2024, February 13). *Statistics: Definition, types, and importance*. Investopedia.
<https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/statistics.asp>
- GeeksforGeeks. (2024a, May 26). *What is Machine Learning?* GeeksforGeeks.
<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/ml-machine-learning/>
- GeeksforGeeks. (2024b, May 29). *Percentile formula*. GeeksforGeeks.
<https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/percentile-formula/>
- Hillier, W. (2023, May 24). Descriptive vs Inferential Statistics Explained. *CareerFoundry*.
<https://careerfoundry.com/en/blog/data-analytics/inferential-vs-descriptive-statistics>
- Hypothesis Testing - Definition, Examples, formula, types*. (n.d.). Cuemath.
<https://www.cuemath.com/data/hypothesis-testing/>
- Kumar, A. (2022, September 6). How to Calculate Age from Date of Birth in SQL? - Scaler Topics. *Scaler Topics*. <https://www.scaler.com/topics/how-to-calculate-age-from-date-of-birth-in-sql/>
- Machine Learning Models - Javatpoint*. (n.d.). www.javatpoint.com.
<https://www.javatpoint.com/machine-learning-models>
- Staff, C. (2023, November 22). *What is statistical analysis? Definition, types, and jobs*. Coursera. <https://www.coursera.org/articles/statistical-analytics>
- Team, S. (2024, January 24). *10 Useful Ways to Visualize Your Data (with Examples)*. Sisense.
<https://www.sisense.com/blog/10-useful-ways-visualize-data-examples/>
- Valchanov, I. (2021, October 16). *How to perform a linear regression in Python (With examples!)*. 365 Data Science. <https://365datascience.com/tutorials/python-tutorials/linear-regression/>

ITDS440 - Assignment Rubric

Student's Full Name: Mony Ho

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Category	Marks Allocation	Marks Attained	Comments
1. Data Cleaning and Preparation	15 marks	12	
2. Exploratory Data Analysis	15 marks	12	
3. Hypothesis Testing	20 marks	14	
4. Regression Analysis	20 marks	15	
5. Machine Learning	20 marks	14	
6. Report and Presentation	10 marks	8	
<p>*** Penalty *** This penalty is for papers that do not meet the assignment requirements. (i.e. word count, format, etc.)</p>	(-5)		
Total marks allocated and achieved:	100 marks	75	